

THE RESEARCH BASE FOR FailureCriteria.com

R. M. Christensen
Stanford University
Aeronautics and Astronautics Department
Stanford CA 94305
christensen@stanford.edu

SUMMARY

A new website on failure criteria for engineering materials is outlined. Included is a new failure form for aligned fiber composite materials. It is fundamentally different from the Tsai-Wu, the Hashin, and the Puck forms, and all other previous forms. The derivation and a realistic, physical application are given.

Keywords: Failure Criteria, Fiber Composites, Yield and Failure

Failure Criteria

The website www.FailureCriteria.com is concerned with the failure characterization for engineering materials. Both isotropic and anisotropic materials are covered. Of special interest are fiber composite materials and the main purpose with that is to develop the anisotropic failure criterion which is the companion piece to the isotropic material treatment, Christensen [1]. A high degree of anisotropy is specified as being typical of the properties for carbon fiber-polymeric matrix systems; it applies to both stiffness and strength.

Using the conditions of high anisotropy along with a polynomial expansion up to terms of second degree for transversely isotropic symmetry, it is found that the failure criterion naturally and necessarily decomposes into two separate failure modes. These are:

Matrix Controlled Failure

$$\left(\frac{1}{T_{22}} - \frac{1}{C_{22}} \right) (\sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33}) + \frac{1}{T_{22} C_{22}} (\sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33})^2 + \frac{1}{S_{23}^2} (\sigma_{23}^2 - \sigma_{22} \sigma_{33}) + \frac{1}{S_{12}^2} (\sigma_{12}^2 + \sigma_{31}^2) \leq 1 \quad (1)$$

Fiber Controlled Failure

$$-C_{11} \leq \sigma_{11} \leq T_{11} \quad (2)$$

The decomposition of composites failure into forms (1) and (2) is entirely new. The matrix controlled form (1) itself is new. The fiber controlled failure form (2) has an interesting history. This form is commonly called the maximum stress criterion. It has always been considered to be a highly useful but totally empirical form for fiber composites. In the present derivation it is not empirical at all, it is a rational and rigorous result of the method, which is based upon the conditions of a high degree of anisotropy, with no subsidiary assumptions. In this connection it can also be observed that the matrix controlled failure criterion, (1), certainly is not a maximum stress form. The two criteria (1) and (2) seem to be very different when compared directly, but the fiber criterion (2) can be written in quadratic form giving it a parallel status to (1).

Discussion and Example

Both (1) and (2) are completely different from the Tsai-Wu [2] and Hashin [3] forms. The main difference between the present forms and the Hashin forms is that no assumptions are involved with the present forms whereas five particular assumptions were necessarily involved in the Hashin derivation. In addition, the Hashin method further decomposes the fiber and matrix controlled modes into sub-modes of either tensile or compressive nature. The isotropic material results of the previous section shows that this “sub-decomposition” is unnecessary and inappropriate.

Following the method given here (or that due to Hashin), under the condition of high anisotropy the failure characterization must decompose into the two separate failure criteria. On this basis, the Tsai-Wu form can only apply to moderately anisotropic systems, that is only for moderate departures from a state of isotropy. It cannot recover the limiting plane strain condition. The other two criteria do not apply under such moderately anisotropic conditions since they do not admit the limiting case of isotropy. They apply in the high anisotropy case typified by carbon-polymer systems. Thus the decomposed failure mode forms apply near one end of the anisotropy scale and recover the plane strain condition while the undecomposed form applies near the other end of the same scale and recovers the isotropy condition.

Using properties for carbon fiber-epoxy matrix systems the failure envelopes for various stress states can be found. The case of axial stress versus equal transverse stresses is as shown in Fig.1.

Fig. 1 3-D Stress State, Eqs. (1) and (2)

For the stress state in Fig. 1 the Hashin form is the same as that in Fig. 1 except that it does not give a lower limit envelope for the stresses. The Tsai-Wu form gives an elliptical envelope.

The corners shown in Fig. 1 are the direct result of the decomposition into separate fiber controlled and matrix controlled modes of failure. This situation is completely parallel to that of the intersecting ductile and brittle failure modes of isotropic materials in the previous section. In physical reality, the corners would be expected to be rounded due to the small misalignment of testing specimens, and due to existing states of damage and specific inhomogeneities, as well as a host of other non-ideal effects. To some extent, this characteristic may also relate to the testing of lamina in isolation as opposed to the stabilized behavior of an in-situ lamina within a laminate. From this point of view, it is certainly best to use the forms directly from the basic failure criteria, (1) and (2), rather than to combine them with some artificial smoothing technique. Another problem with the regions around corners in failure surfaces is the extreme difficulty in generating reliable multi-axial test data. It is very much more difficult than that for one dimensional strength tests. It is argued that most of these effects are best treated at the laminate scale where damage is commonly considered.

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References

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